

DOES MISINFORMATION ON SOCIAL MEDIA AFFECT FOOD CONSUMPTION BEHAVIOR? INSIGHTS FROM BANGLADESH

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Abstract

In digital communication, social media offers numerous benefits for individuals and businesses, including building networks, facilitating collaboration, and promoting products. However, the rapid and widespread dissemination of misinformation about food on these platforms diminishes the public's ability to identify reliable sources. In this division of time, understanding the impact of social media food misinformation on consumers' food behavior is essential. A survey was conducted among over 200 consumers of the Dhaka South City Corporation. The results indicate that individuals with higher educational attainment and those who use YouTube and trust bloggers for food information are more susceptible to misinformation. While misinformation regarding the keto diet and food supplements showed statistically significant results, it was also found that it can temporarily deter consumers from eating certain foods, such as Sultan Dines biryani. Moreover, 25% of respondents share viral posts on social media without knowing the news is true. Promoting digital literacy through workshops and awareness campaigns is crucial in helping consumers differentiate between reliable information and misinformation. Additionally, strengthening regulatory frameworks and implementing stricter laws are essential to preventing the spread of misinformation.

Keywords: Food misinformation, Social media, Consumer behavior, Bangladesh

1. Introduction

In the era of digital communication, social media has brought a 'revolutionary' change not only in the traditional modes of knowledge production, transfer, mobilization, and sharing (Leonardi, 2017; Chowdhury & Odame, 2013) but also in the patterns of human interaction, social engagement, civic life, and building social relationship (Boulianne, 2019; Sabatovych, 2019). Beyond traditional media, social media can serve as a valuable platform for accessing food safety information due to its accessibility and information-gathering capabilities (Kuttschreuter et al., 2014). With over 3.6 billion individuals using social media platforms (Statista, 2021), an increasing number of users have spread misinformation, disinformation, and misleading news

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(Valenzuela et al., 2020; Abrams & Greenhawt, 2020). Among diverse issues, misleading information about food safety is flooded on social media (Hoel, 2019; Lelieveld & Andersen, 2019) that has become “a serious problem” in many jurisdictions such as China (Wang et al., 2020) and Malaysia (Soon, 2021). In the United States, misinformation about genetically modified (GM) foods has claimed that “GM foods were not safe” and “FDA’s (Food and Drug Administration) policy was not supported by scientific evidence” (Wang, 2021, p. 461). In the wake of misinformation about food safety, the concept of “real food” has become a popular theme on online media platforms (Ramachandran et al., 2018). In Canada, social media platforms have become convenient for spreading “fake news” and misleading information about foods, the COVID-19 pandemic, vaccines, health, and nutrition (Rubin, 2019; Gruzd & Mai, 2020; Atkinson, 2021)

World Economic Forum (WEF) in 2024 identifies misinformation as the top perceived global crisis posing severe economic and societal threats (Gingerich, 2024). Misinformation about a range of issues (e.g., health, nutrition, vaccination, disaster, government, and election) is posted on social media outlets (Valenzuela et al., 2020; Domgaard & Park, 2021; O’Connor & Murphy, 2021; Zucker, 2020; Pan et al., 2021). Like many other nations, Bangladesh has been dealing with the consequences of inaccurate or misleading information on media platforms since the 2000s, when the media business started to flourish (Hoque, 2014). Unfortunately, the food industry in Bangladesh has not been immune to this phenomenon. In recent years, several instances of fake food news have circulated, causing unnecessary panic and confusion among consumers. A member of the Food Safety Authority in Bangladesh claims that fancy advertisements and fake labels often fool ordinary people, despite containing untrue statements about products in advertisements (The Asian Age, 2018). The verified Facebook page of Horlicks Bangladesh, with 390,000 followers, claims that drinking Horlicks can make children taller, stronger, and sharper, and improve their ability to concentrate better than others, despite lacking scientific proof (Hossain, 2018). Another example involved a viral message claiming that a specific cooking oil brand had miraculous health benefits. The message spread rapidly through social media platforms, leading many individuals to switch to this brand without proper research. Subsequently, it was discovered that the claims were exaggerated and lacked scientific evidence (Hossain, 2018). Another misinformation that mainly spreads in rural Bangladesh is that if someone eats Indian Pennywort (*Centella Asiatica*, Thankuni in Bengali), coronavirus will not be able to affect that person (Mostafiz, 2021).

The spread of misinformation and fake news on social media generates confusion, challenges the legitimacy and credibility of information, modifies human behavior, and undermines consumers’ confidence (Bennett & Livingston, 2018; Abrams & Greenhawt, 2020). Misleading information is now considered an emerging challenge to food safety best management practices as it can erode consumers’ trust in food safety systems (Whitworth, 2020). Fake food safety information shared on social media results in the loss of revenue in some countries (e.g., Malaysia) as it fuels panic and mistrust among consumers (Soon, 2021). As food misinformation on social media becomes more prevalent, government officials, journalists, and civil society members in Bangladesh are increasingly expressing growing concerns about the significant amount of misleading information available to consumers. This situation threatens

consumers' trust in the information shared by public institutions, which could ultimately undermine safety and social cohesion.

1.1 Objectives of the Study

In the age of social media, information spreads like wildfire, often without any fact-checking or verification. Unfortunately, this phenomenon is not limited to politics or celebrity gossip; it also extends to misinformation about food. Misinformation spreads rapidly across social media platforms like Facebook, YouTube, and Instagram, as users often share and repost content without verifying its credibility. This behavior can weaken consumers' trust in food safety systems.

- i) To explore the impact of social media food misinformation on consumer behavior.
- ii) To investigate the subjective factors contributing to belief in food misinformation on social media.

To achieve these objectives, the study will address the following research questions:

- i. How does social media food misinformation impact consumer behavior?
- ii. What subjective factors lead consumers to accept food misinformation from social media?

2. Literature Review

2.1 Social Media and Misinformation

Social media is a web-based application that enables users to create and share content. It has emerged as a key source of information for individuals who use the internet (Kumar, 2014). Information is spread on social media by individual users, the government, and various collective groups (e.g., business organizations and charitable institutions), and intentions behind sharing information can range from curiosity and justification to status-seeking and concern for others' welfare (Chowdhury et al., 2023). The rise of social media platforms has undeniably transformed our communication, connections, and information consumption. While it has undoubtedly brought numerous benefits, social media's unchecked growth has also given birth to a concerning issue: the spread of misinformation. Baccarella (2018) refers to social media as a "Web of deceit" and highlights the strength of misinformation waves on digital platforms. Social media and its relation to misinformation have become a noticeable research topic among scholars.

Typically, online misinformation refers to the dissemination of information through digital platforms, such as social media, websites, or messaging apps, either intentionally or unintentionally, without a factual foundation, confirmation, or clarification (Sille, 2017). It can manifest in various forms, including fabricated news articles, manipulated images or videos, misleading headlines, and deceptive social media posts. Unverified information on social media is often referred to by common names such as disinformation, misinformation, and fake news. Wardle and Derakhshan (2017) describe a category called "mis-dis-mal-information," which refers to a type of information disorder. Misinformation refers explicitly to false or inaccurate

information that is unintentionally spread. It can result from genuine mistakes, misinterpretation, or lack of fact-checking. Misinformation can range from harmless rumors to misleading health advice or false historical events (Lin et al., 2023). The key aspect of misinformation is that it is not created with the intent to deceive (Wardle & Derakhshan, 2017). A typical example of misinformation on social media is the spread of false health claims. For instance, a post claiming that lemon and lemon juice can cure cancer gained traction on various platforms (Parthasarathy, 2022). Despite being scientifically debunked (Brown, 2022), the post was shared many times, leading some individuals to believe in its efficacy. Misinformation, on the other hand, is purposefully inaccurate or misleading information that is disseminated to deceive or manipulate. It is often used for political purposes, propaganda, or to create chaos and confusion (Chen et al., 2023). It is essential to distinguish between misinformation and disinformation; disinformation refers to the act of misleading others through the use of false information. (Chowdhury et al., 2023). Similar to propaganda, disinformation is often disseminated by individuals, organizations, and even governments, all of which work to serve their interests (Stiftung, 2020). The dissemination of disinformation can lead to profound consequences, especially within the political domain, where it may be exploited to weaken democratic institutions and processes (Brennen et al., 2020). Additionally, disinformation poses serious risks to public health, safety, and overall well-being, as it can distort facts and hinder effective decision-making (Vosoughi, Roy, & Aral, 2018).

Numerous studies have examined the different aspects that influence the spread of misleading information on social media (Luo et al., 2021; Pennycook et al., 2021; Zubiaga et al., 2016). These studies have highlighted the challenge of distinguishing between accurate information and misinformation, as they are frequently intertwined. The public's misperception of incorrect information as accurate is the main reason it spreads disinformation on social media (Pennycook et al., 2021). Misinformation spreads rapidly on social media due to its ability to evoke strong emotions (Ma, 2008) and appeal to pre-existing beliefs (Allcott & Gentzkow, 2017). People are likelier to share content that aligns with their personal views or desires without critically evaluating its validity (Allcott & Gentzkow, 2017). Peer influence also contributes to the propagation of misinformation. People tend to trust the information their friends or connections share on social media platforms, even if it lacks credibility (Santoso et al., 2020). Literature also shows that a lack of digital media literacy is responsible for the public's general faith in the false information propagated on social media. The public's capacity to recognize misinformation can be improved by information literacy (Jones-Jang, 2021).

2.2 Food Misinformation on Social Media in Bangladesh

Social media has become an indispensable part of human life, helping to access, create, share, and spread news and information within a second. It also supports communication with others locally and globally. Bangladesh is an impoverished South Asian country where 49.55 million people will be using social media in 2022 (Kemp, 2022), and the number of internet operators in Bangladesh is growing faster than ever. According to Statcounter Global Stats (2023), Facebook (90.52%), YouTube (5.11) %, Twitter (1.5) %, Instagram (1.18) %, LinkedIn (1.01) %, and Pinterest (.5%), TikTok,

and Snapchat are some of the prominent social media platforms in Bangladesh. Considering the influential roles, the application of social media in different spheres of life, including the food sector, has rapidly grown in Bangladesh (Bednarz & Orelly, 2020). For instance, numerous social media outlets (e.g., Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Blogs, and YouTube) are increasingly being used by Bangladeshi food producers and local food stakeholders to share information, increase consumer awareness, change consumer behavior, raise funds, build innovation networks, enhance community engagement, and circulate capacity development as well as innovative activities (Bednarz & Orelly, 2020).

Bangladesh has emerged as one of the top three nations with the highest levels of Facebook activity (Prothom Alo, 2023). Thus, in Bangladesh, social media platforms have become a convenient venue for spreading “fake news” and misleading information about foods, the COVID-19 pandemic, vaccines, education and health, nutrition, crime, human rights, religious, and entertainment as people are adopting this information (Al-zaman et al., 2020). A recent survey reveals that despite providing “conflicting” and “confusing” opinions, ordinary people in Bangladesh still believe in social media, especially Facebook and YouTube, for food decisions and food-related nutrition information (Raisa, 2020). There are many cases of misleading food information in Bangladesh. For instance, drinking hot water with salt, lemon, ginger, garlic, black cumin, cloves, and black pepper can help cure COVID-19, as reported by 203k media users in 2020 (Islam & Siddque, 2020). Another piece of misinformation that mainly spreads in rural Bangladesh is that consuming Indian Pennywort (*Centella asiatica*, Thankuni in Bengali) will prevent the coronavirus from affecting that person (Mostafiz, 2021).

False claims about certain foods' nutritional value or harmful effects can lead to unhealthy dietary choices. A nutritionist from BIRDEM Hospital mentions that her 30 patients who underwent hospitalization after following misinformation and poor advice from online content about food, such as canned proteins, can develop muscle (Maswood, 2020). On social media, false stories claiming that artificial eggs are being sold in marketplaces have been extensively shared. The Bangladesh Food Safety Authority (BFSA) has categorically denied the existence of fake eggs in the nation. It has been reported that labeled reports are being sold in local markets as "a hoax" (Shaon, 2017). Many people become confused and distrustful, modifying their eating habits due to such unconfirmed content. Similar news spread about ‘plastic rice’ in the Bangladesh Gaibandha district, which agricultural experts later proved to be real rice, not made with plastic (The Daily Star, 2019).

For food businesses, false media news can be detrimental to their reputation. Negative reviews or false accusations spread through online platforms can tarnish the image of a restaurant, food delivery service, or any other food-related establishment. Even if the news is proven false later on, the damage may already be done, resulting in a loss of customers and revenue. For example, Sultan's Dine, a well-known restaurant chain in Dhaka city, has been blamed for using meat from animals other than goats to make kacchi biriyani on a Facebook post that went viral on other social media platforms (The Business Standard, 2023). Later on, the body of consumer rights clarified that there was no concrete evidence that Sultan's Dine used meat from animals other than goats.

2.3 The Perils of Misinformation on Social Media and Its Impact on Consumers

Consumers are now increasingly concerned about the price, origin, and harvesting procedures of food products. They also care about whether these foods are safe, healthy, and free from allergens, as well as whether they contain organic components (Dipika & Haghiri, 2020; Dipika, 2019). However, social media platforms have revolutionized the way information is shared and consumed. Misinformation can easily infiltrate people's news feeds and timelines, influencing their opinions and beliefs. Individuals often perceive such statements as facts, even without scientific evidence. One prime example is the false claim that coconut oil enhances cognition and focus (Lundahl, 2017). While coconut oil has benefits, scientific evidence supporting its cognitive effects is limited.

Moreover, consumers exposed to misinformation on social media may experience cognitive biases, such as confirmation bias or the illusory truth effect. These biases can impact their perception of reality and influence their decision-making processes. One instance is the fabricated statement that the FDA declared Frosted Flakes healthier than avocados (Lundahl, 2017). Such misleading information can cause confusion among consumers, impacting their perception of healthy food choices and potentially harming businesses that promote more nutritious alternatives. Food misinformation has distinct effects on businesses and consumers. False information exposes businesses to unfavorable outcomes, such as product boycotts and damaged brand reputations, by altering consumers' knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors toward certain brands or products (Domenico et al., 2021). The food businesses heavily rely on consumers' trust and credibility. Numerous studies (Rapp & Salovich, 2018; Lewandowsky et al., 2012) have shown that exposure to misinformation on social media can undermine these crucial aspects and significantly influence consumer decision-making processes. As misleading information spreads, consumers may hesitate to purchase certain products, opt for alternatives, or even avoid entire food categories. For example, the large multinational Pepsi faced product boycotts due to online misinformation (Obada, 2019). So, brands can encounter financial (Binham, 2019) and reputational damage (Berthon & Pitt, 2018) due to the circulation of misinformation on social media.

The media in Bangladesh recently disseminated misinformation regarding a study conducted by Bushra et al. (2022) on identifying metal contamination in top soils and brinjal fruits, alleging that eating brinjal can cause cancer. The research did not conclude that eating brinjal directly causes cancer. Instead, it highlighted the presence of trace amounts of metals in both the soil and brinjal fruits. These findings should be interpreted in a balanced manner, considering their overall impact on human health. False claims or negative narratives about ingredients, processing methods, or health hazards associated with brands can significantly impact public perception (Visentin et al., 2019). Social media platforms have developed into a haven for product promotions and endorsements in the era of influencer culture. This issue is worrisome due to its potential to mislead individuals and lead them to incorrect choices, resulting in economic setbacks and its influence on various domains such as health and medicine. Dissemination of incorrect treatments and misguided advice through misinformation can further exacerbate the damage inflicted on the public's overall physical and mental well-being (Sille, 2017). Influencers—including registered dietitians—are frequently trusted by consumers for their skill in delivering trustworthy health-related

information. However, The Washington Post recently exposed an alarming trend in which dietitians, expected to provide unbiased nutritional advice, were found to endorse aspartame and sugar in social media posts without fully disclosing their association with food and beverage industry groups (Nelson, 2023). Endorsements lacking clear disclosure from credible professionals can lead to confusion among the general public, potentially resulting in misinformed dietary choices and adverse health effects. A recent study on Pinterest sheds light on the alarming trend of for-profit companies exploiting health-related tags, particularly in the context of cancer nutrition. This study found that nearly half of the posts tagged under nutrition for cancer were created by profit-driven entities, many of which marketed products claiming to prevent, treat, or cure cancer (Nelson, 2023). This discovery underscores the importance of scrutinizing and raising awareness about the potential risks of misleading health claims on social media. Marketing products such as vitamin supplements under the guise of cancer prevention or treatment is not only misleading but also potentially dangerous, which can lead to confusion, misplaced hope, and potentially harmful decisions (Nelson, 2023).

3. Methodology of the Study

3.1 Research Technique

A researcher must choose the appropriate methods for gathering and analyzing data and fully comprehend these methods to utilize them (Babbie, 1998). Bryman and Bell (2007) propose that any social issue analysis is best done using a quantitative approach. Here, the research objective of how food misinformation on social media affects consumers' behavior in Bangladesh falls within the heading of social behavior. A quantitative technique was employed in this study.

3.2 Study Population and Sample Size

Dhaka South City Corporation has been chosen as a study area in this study. All individuals living in the Dhaka South City Corporation who are at least 19 years old or older and have purchased goods from supermarkets (Shwapno, Agora, and Meenabazar) were considered part of the population for this study. From this demographic, a total of 200 participants, comprising both males and females, were selected as the study's sample size. This study employed a mall intercept interview to collect information using the non-probability convenience sample technique, as supermarkets in Dhaka South City Corporation are easily accessible and visited by a diverse range of people. Because of this, shopping in these supermarkets is a good way for shoppers to find a variety of food. By talking to these shoppers, researchers can gather information from a group of people that represents the wider population of food consumers in the area. This helps ensure that the data collected is useful and accurately reflects the habits and opinions of most food buyers in Dhaka South City. Respondents were informed that the survey aimed to gather their opinions on food-related misinformation on social media, thereby reducing sample bias.

3.3 Sources of Data

This research employed primary and secondary data collection methods to obtain the most optimal responses to the research inquiries. An extensive search was conducted using the Google Scholar search engine to ensure the acquisition of reliable secondary

documents. This search encompassed peer-reviewed journal articles, books, newspapers, reports, government websites, conference papers, and published and unpublished theses. The search utilized keywords related to misinformation, disinformation, malinformation, and fake information about food on social media, as well as the perils of food misinformation, consumers' perception of misinformation about food, and the influence of online food misinformation on consumers.

The principal method used to gather most of the necessary data in this study was primary data collection techniques. The primary data for this research were collected using a structured questionnaire survey, and each questionnaire took approximately ten minutes to complete.

3.4 Data Analysis

This study analyzed the impact of food misinformation on consumers' confidence in the food safety system in Bangladesh by using a binary logistic regression model. To prepare for the analysis, the sample data were entered into an Excel worksheet, and summary descriptive statistics of the responses were generated using the IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The information gathered from the respondents was reviewed, validated, and revised as needed for completeness, accuracy, and reliability.

3.5 Binary Logistic Regression Model

Due to its ability to forecast probabilities between 0 and 1, the logistic model is employed in this study as an analytical tool. This relationship is expressed as a function of $\pi_i = \pi(X_i)$, where π_i is the previously mentioned likelihood of the impact of food misinformation on consumers' behavior, and X_i is the explanatory variable. Logistic regression estimates a multiple linear regression function:

$$\text{Log}(\pi_i / 1 - \pi_i) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{i1} + \beta_2 X_{i2} + \dots + \beta_n X_{in} + \varepsilon_i$$

('i' is used for ith individual)

When two or more independent variables are thought to impact one or more dependent variables, multiple regression analysis is typically employed in that research (Field, 2013; Cohen et al., 2013). A binary logistic regression model differs from a regression model using a binary or dichotomous outcome variable.

Through the model, this study explores the underlying variables that drive consumers to believe in food misinformation and how this misinformation influences consumers' food decisions. Three categories of explanatory variables were selected for the model: 1) demographic variables, 2) attitudinal variables, and 3) knowledge variables. The model will examine the effect of consumers' knowledge about food misinformation and how their demographic characteristics impact their judgment about food consumption. So, in this study, to predict the impact of food misinformation on consumers' behavior in the food safety system, the following regression model is developed:

$$\text{Consumers' Food Behavior} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Female} + \beta_2 \text{Age2} + \beta_3 \text{Age3} + \beta_4 \text{Age4} + \beta_5 \text{Educ2} + \beta_6 \text{Edu3} + \beta_7 \text{Edu4} + \beta_8 \text{Use YT} + \beta_9 \text{Use Intgm} + \beta_{10} \text{Use LdIn} + \beta_{11} \text{Plastic rice} + \beta_{12} \text{Sultan dine} + \beta_{13} \text{Covid19} + \beta_{14} \text{Keto Diet} + \beta_{15} \text{F.S muscle} + \beta_{16} \text{Horlicks} + \beta_{17}$$

$$\text{Share News} + \beta_{18} \text{Check Authority} + \beta_{19} \text{Trust celeb} + \beta_{20} \text{Trust B. Firms} + \beta_{21} \text{Trust bloggers} + \beta_{22} \text{Trust Scientists} + \beta_{23} \text{Info S.A} + \beta_{24} \text{Info A} + \beta_{25} \text{Info N} + \beta_{26} \text{Behave S.A} + \beta_{27} \text{Behave A} + \beta_{28} \text{Behave N} + \varepsilon_i \quad (1)$$

One group from each group-category independent dummy variable was removed to avoid perfect collinearity in the model. Some groups considered the base group were male respondents, respondents between 20 and 30 years old, participants with a high school or less school degree, and respondents who used Facebook as a social media platform.

4. Empirical Analysis

Descriptive statistics offer concise summaries of the sample. In this study, the dummy variables are described using descriptive statistics. Gender, age, education, used social media applications, recent food misinformation instances in Bangladesh, reaction to food safety news on social media, trusted sources for food safety information on social media, and the usefulness of social media for creating awareness among consumers are the explanatory variables of this study.

4.1 Summary Statistics for the Variables

Table 1: Variable descriptions for the logistic regression model

Variable Name	Frequency	Mean	Standard Deviation (S.D)
Gender			
Male*	108	.54	.500
Female	92	.46	.500
Age			
Between 20 and 30 years *	29	.15	.353
Between 31 and 40 years	66	.33	.472
Between 41 and 60 years	86	.43	.496
More than 60 years of age	18	.09	.287
Education			
High school or less than high school *	15	.08	.264
College or higher professional degree	35	.18	.381
Bachelor Degree	67	.34	.473
Master's degree and above	82.	.41	.493
Utilized Social Media Application			
Facebook*	189	.95	.229

YouTube	195	.98	.157
Instagram	105	.53	.501
LinkedIn	26	.13	.353
Food Misinformation Instances in Bangladesh			
Fake Egg*	45	.23	.419
Plastic Rice	29	.15	.353
Sultan Dine's Biryani	152	.76	.428
Drinking hot water with salt, hot water with lemon, ginger, garlic, black cumin, cloves, and black pepper can cure Covid-19	170	.85	.358
Keto Diet is Safe	31	.16	.363
Food Supplements can improve muscle	31	.16	.363
Horlicks can make children tall	188	.94	.247
Reaction to the viral post about food on Social Media			
Ignore It*	128	.64	.481
Share it	50	.25	.434
Check the claim with the proper authorities	22	.11	.314
Trusted Sources of Food Information			
Shared by scientists	109	.55	.499
Shared by friends and family*	34	.17	.377
Shared by celebrities	8	.04	.196
Shared by food business firms	15	.08	.264
Shared by food bloggers	30	.15	.358
Social Media is the Prime Source of food-safety Information			
Strongly Agree	61	.31	.462
Agree	93	.47	.500
Neutral	22	.11	.314
Disagree*	24	.12	.326
Social media can help consumers behave more sensibly by sharing food safety information			

Strongly Agree			
Agree	76	.38	.487
Neutral	91	.46	.499
Disagree*	25	.13	.332
	7	.04	.184

Source: Sample data

The descriptive statistics of the sample observations are shown in Table 1. There were 101 female participants (46 percent) out of the 200 respondents. The age range of the bulk of study participants (43%) was 41–60 years old. Most responders fall into an age bracket where a person can experience a rise in their degree of financial independence, enabling them to increase their expenditure on nutritious meals. Higher education often correlates with higher income potential. Individuals with higher degrees may have more disposable income to spend on groceries and prefer the quality and variety available at supermarkets. 41% of participants in this survey held a master's degree. Facebook (95%) and YouTube (98%) were the study participants' most widely used social media sites. There were only three respondents, all of whom were female, who did not use social media. Horlicks can make children tall (94%), Sultan Dine's uses meat other than mutton in its Biryani (76%), Consumption of hot water with salt, hot water with lemon, ginger, garlic, black cumin, cloves, and black pepper can cure Covid-19 (84%) were the food incidents in Bangladesh about whom most of the respondents heard. However, they were unaware that these instances were untrue. A significant portion of the study participants, 64%, mentioned ignoring news articles about food safety on social media if they perceived them as fake. This suggests a level of skepticism among users regarding the authenticity of such articles. Additionally, only 11% of respondents mentioned verifying the news's veracity, while a more significant percentage, 25%, admitted to frequently sharing posts on social media without verifying the allegations with the appropriate authorities. These findings highlight the importance of critical thinking and fact-checking when it comes to consuming and sharing information on social media platforms, especially about sensitive topics like food safety. 60.2% of the participants expressed trust in the news from scientists as a reliable source of food safety information. This suggests that scientific expertise and research-based information hold significant credibility among consumers. The survey revealed that some respondents also considered friends and family (17%), food bloggers (15%), and business firms (8%) as reliable sources of food safety information. This suggests that individuals may rely on various sources, including online influencers and industry-related entities, to gather information about food safety. 61.2% agree they obtain most of their food-related information from social media. The survey also wanted to determine whether food safety information shared on social media promotes responsible consumer behavior. According to the survey results, 47.8% of the respondents agree that food safety information shared on social media promotes responsible consumer behavior.

4.2 Results and Discussion

Table 2: Estimated Coefficients

Variable Name	Coefficient	Std. Error	Significance	Expect. Coef.
1. Female	-1.588	1.351	.240	.204
Age2	-4.239	2.570	.099	.014
Age3	-4.400	2.664	.099	.012
Age4	-3.254	2.509	.195	.039
Edu2	2.482	2.333	.287	11.965
Edu3	5.360	2.663	.044	212.630
Edu4	5.577	2.654	.036	264.161
Use YT	2.112	2.728	.049	8.261
Use intgm	2.824	1.767	.110	16.848
Use LdIn	-.979	2.435	.688	.376
Plastic rice	.107	1.739	.951	1.113
Sultan dine	1.119	1.263	.376	3.062
Covid19	-.412	1.421	.772	.663
Keto Diet	5.005	2.514	.046	149.176
F.S muscle	6.478	2.890	.025	650.698
Horlicks	4.950	3.038	.103	141.245
Share News	3.691	1.577	.019	40.092
Check Authority	-.096	1.852	.959	.908
Trust celeb	-.440	3.588	.902	.644
Trust B Firms	-2.890	2.713	.287	.056
Trust bloggers	-3.605	2.143	.053	.027
Trust Scientist	-.157	1.396	.910	.854
Info S.A	-26.008	3683.616	.994	.000
Info A	-17.948	3683.615	.996	.000
Info N	15.230	5128.368	.998	4115606.974
Behave S.A	-1.379	6.240	.825	.252
Behave A	3.376	6.409	.598	29.259
Behave N	6.290	6.982	.368	539.039

Source: Sample data

The parameters of the logistic regression model, specified in equation (1), were

estimated by the maximum likelihood (ML) approach using IBM SPSS. The dependent variable (Consumers' FoodBehavior) was coded 1, indicating the impact of food misinformation on social media on individuals' food consumption behavior; otherwise, it is 0 (null hypothesis). Table 2 shows the estimation results of the logistic regression model.

Keeping all other variables equal, each coefficient (β) shows how the log odds of the result change with a one-unit increase in the predictor variable. A positive coefficient indicates that as the predictor variable increases, the log odds of the outcome occurring also increase.

Some independent variables in Table 3, such as education (Edu3) and (Edu4), Utilized Social Media Applications (Use YT), Keto Diet is Safe (Keto Diet); Food Supplements can improve muscle (F. S muscle), Reaction to viral posts about food on Social Media (Share news), Trusted Sources of Food Information (Trust bloggers) had statistically significant effects on the dependent variable.

The results show that consumers with bachelor's and master's degrees were 212.63 and 264.16 units more impacted by misinformation on social media, respectively, than participants who have completed high school or less. This is even though it is expected that highly educated people will not likely be impacted by misinformation on social media. It indicates that the effects of false information on social media can be complex and vary depending on a person's educational background, among other things. Due to this complexity, they may become more susceptible to misinformation, leading to misunderstandings or misinterpretations. Social media frequently operates within peer-to-peer content-sharing networks. Higher-educated people could feel pressure to participate in the newest debates or trends, which could cause them to spread unverified information to stay relevant in their networks. So, higher education does not ensure that people are immune to misinformation, even though it may increase digital literacy to some degree. They might rely more on their ability to assess information critically, which could lead to oversight. While higher educational degrees may provide individuals with a foundation for critical thinking and research skills, it is crucial for everyone to actively engage in fact-checking, cross-referencing information, and seeking reliable sources to make informed decisions about food safety.

The coefficient of the variable (Use YT) was 2.21 and statistically significant at the 0.49 level, which implied that when all other factors were held constant, the respondents who preferred using YouTube as a social media platform were more affected by false information than those who preferred using Facebook. YouTube video content might be seen as more reliable or authoritative than Facebook text-based content. YouTube's monetization method, which rewards creators based on views and engagement, may incite the production of sensational or misleading content, such as inaccurate food information. Content creators can prioritize views and clicks over accuracy and reliability.

Additionally, the results indicated that the dummy variables' coefficients, which mentioned the individuals exposed to false information on social media regarding the safety of the Keto diet and the ability of food supplements to build muscle, were positive and significant at the 0.46 and 0.025 levels. This suggested that *ceteris paribus*, the likelihood of these respondent groups being influenced by misinformation was

1491.8 and 6506.9 times higher than those who heard about Fake Egg. The coefficient of the misinformation about Sultan Dines Biryani was positive. Some interviewees stated that they temporarily stopped consuming Sultan Dines' biriyani after discovering that the restaurant utilized meat other than a goat.

Based on the research findings, it is evident that only 11% of the respondents in this study checked online food safety information with the proper authority. Additionally, 25% of the respondents shared food safety news without verifying its credibility. The coefficient of variable Share News is positive and statistically significant at the 0.19 level. From these results, it can be concluded that consumers who share online food information sources without verifying their credibility are 400 times more likely to adopt misinformation than the respondents who ignore online food information. On the other hand, the coefficient of the variable Check Authority is negative. It highlights the importance of critically evaluating and verifying the credibility of online food information sources to avoid falling victim to misinformation.

A significant number of respondents (more than 50%) identified scientists as trustworthy sources of information, which suggests that these consumers possess the ability to distinguish between credible and non-credible sources. Therefore, the likelihood of them being misled by misinformation is minimal. Besides scientists (55%), a significant percentage of respondents considered their friends and family (17%) and food bloggers (15%) as credible sources of food safety knowledge. The dummy variables' coefficients for bloggers are negative. A negative coefficient suggests that as food bloggers' influence or activity increases, the impact of social media misinformation on consumers decreases. This can imply that food bloggers, potentially through positive content, fact-checking, or building trust, help mitigate the adverse effects of misinformation.

According to Table 4, Behave S.A. is the final explanatory variable, and its coefficient is negative. The negative coefficient indicates that respondents who believe that social media can help consumers behave more sensibly by sharing food safety information were less impacted by food misinformation on social media.

Table 3: Variables in the Equation

Variables in the Equation					
B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
2.041	.222	84.764	1	<.001	7.696

The Wald statistic tests the null hypothesis that the coefficient (B) equals zero indicating no effect. Here, a Wald value of 84.764 indicates a statistically significant effect.

The larger the Wald statistic, the more evidence there is against the null hypothesis.

The output indicates that the variable in question has a statistically significant positive effect on the dependent variable (impact). The effect is substantial, as indicated by the odds ratio of 7.696, suggesting that the presence of this variable dramatically increases the odds of the dependent outcome occurring.

Table 4: Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients

Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients				
		Chi-square	df	Sig.
Step 1	Step	102.331	28	<.001
	Block	102.331	28	<.001
	Model	102.331	28	<.001

The Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients provide strong evidence that the model, which includes multiple predictors, significantly explains the variability in the dependent variable. The Chi-square statistic is relatively high (102.331), and the significance level was extremely low ($p < .001$), which rejected the null hypothesis.

Table 5: Model Summary

Step	-2 Log likelihood	Cox & Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R Square
1	40.407 ^a	.400	.785

Source: Sample data

In this case, the -2 log-likelihood is relatively low (40.407), indicating a good fit of the data to the model. The Cox & Snell R square value (.400) suggests that the model's predictor variables can explain approximately 40% of the dependent variable variance. Nagelkerke R square (.785) suggests that the model explains approximately 78.5% of the variance in the dependent variable

5. Conclusion and policy implications

Social media has evolved into a powerful tool for disseminating information in recent years. Furthermore, it might serve as a haven for misinformation. Food and agriculture are also affected by this misinformation epidemic, which extends beyond political and social topics. Ignoring the detrimental consequences of this spread in the era of fake news and internet disinformation is impossible. Bangladesh, being an agrarian country with a rich culinary heritage, is not immune to the dissemination of online food misinformation. This article presents key findings from a structured questionnaire survey that examines the factors contributing to the acceptance of food misinformation and the extent to which misinformation culture influences customers' dietary behavior patterns, using a binary logistic regression model. Factors including the use of YouTube as a social media platform, sharing viral news about food on social media, and trusting bloggers as a trusted source of food information contributed to the acceptance of food misinformation. Additionally, the findings suggest that individuals with higher educational backgrounds were more susceptible to misinformation about food than those with lower levels of education.

Based on these findings, this study recommends several policies. First, comprehensive

nutrition education programs that encourage critical analysis of food information should be implemented. These programs could include workshops and awareness campaigns to inform the public about the risks associated with food misinformation. In Bangladesh, consumers can consult local authorities, such as the Ministry of Food or agricultural extension offices, for accurate and up-to-date information on food safety and agricultural practices. By following these practices, consumers in Bangladesh can effectively navigate the online environment and make informed food choices. Additionally, it is essential to strengthen laws regulating food marketing, particularly concerning health claims. Ensuring that advertising claims are backed by scientific evidence can help reduce confusion among educated consumers.

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